

Solvent effect on protonation equilibria of L-ornithine and L-glutamic acid

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An electrometric investigation of protonation equilibria of L-ornithine and L-glutamic acid in aqua-*N,N'*-dimethylformamide media of varying composition (0–60%, v/v) has been made at different concentrations of the amino acid at 303 K and an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³. The best fit chemical models are arrived at based on firm statistical grounds employing crystallographic *R* factor, χ^2 , skewness and kurtosis. The variation in the protonation constants with the dielectric constant of the medium is attributed to the electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

Investigations of acidobasic equilibria of amino acids, their interaction with metal ions in media of varied ionic strength, temperature and dielectric constant throw light on the mechanism of enzyme catalyzed reactions. Although it is known that the polarity of the active site cavities in proteins is lower than that of the bulk, a direct measurement of dielectric constant is not possible. Sigel *et al.*¹ invoked a method wherein comparison of formation constants obtained from acidobasic and/or metal complex equilibria with the corresponding values observed at the biological centre offers a way to estimate an effective dielectric constant or equivalent solution dielectric constant for the cavity. In continuation of our studies in aqua-organic media² a thorough investigation of complex equilibria of amino acids has been taken up employing rigorous mathematical procedures for obtaining the best fit chemical model and studying solute-solvent interactions.

Results and Discussion

Most of the amino acids act as tridentate ligands. When the third donor site of the amino acid is a nitrogen atom, marked tridentate behavior is frequently found, more so when the additional chelation results in a five- or six-membered ring. Nitrogen donor atoms can associate with hydrogen ions in physiological pH ranges. Hence, there is often significant competition between hydrogen and metal ions for this third donor site. This situation results in the simultaneous existence of a number of equilibria, producing an array of successively protonated complexes. So an insight into the protonation-deprotonation equilibria of L-ornithine and L-glutamic acid is very much helpful in understanding the metal-ligand equilibria associated with these ligands.

Typical alkalimetric titration and formation curves for L-

Table 1. Best fit chemical models of acidobasic equilibria of L-ornithine in water-DMF mixtures

$\mu = 0.16 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 303 K										
% (v/v)	log β_1 (SD)	log β_2 (SD)	log β_3 (SD)	pH range	NP	U_{corr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ^2	<i>R</i>
00.0	10.53 (0.01)	19.38 (0.02)	21.22 (0.01)	1.8–10.7	81	0.231	2.40	13.49	55.88	0.005
10.0	10.36 (0.01)	19.11 (0.01)	20.98 (0.01)	2.0–10.7	63	2.638	1.86	10.56	40.22	0.006
20.0	10.39 (0.01)	19.11 (0.01)	21.24 (0.01)	1.9–10.7	94	1.149	1.03	5.69	10.81	0.003
30.0	10.28 (0.01)	18.97 (0.01)	21.30 (0.02)	2.5–10.8	68	5.963	1.54	8.43	45.76	0.011
40.0	9.95 (0.01)	18.40 (0.01)	20.81 (0.03)	2.6–10.6	52	6.863	1.72	8.86	30.00	0.011
50.0	10.01 (0.01)	18.55 (0.02)	21.25 (0.05)	3.0–10.7	62	4.486	1.68	8.81	38.06	0.016
60.0	9.72 (0.03)	18.34 (0.02)	21.73 (0.06)	3.5–10.8	63	3.265	1.99	8.96	39.59	0.028

No. of titration curves in each percentage = 4.

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(NP-m) \times 10^N$, where *m* = number of species.

Table 2. Best fit chemical models of acidobasic equilibria of L-glutamic acid in water-DMF mixtures

$\mu = 0.16 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp = 303 K										
%	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$	pH range	NP	U_{con}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ^2	R
(v/v)	(SD)	(SD)	(SD)							
00.0	9.65 (0.01)	13.48 (0.01)	16.03 (0.01)	2.0-10.0	82	4.357	0.92	6.47	13.27	0.002
10.0	9.63 (0.01)	13.97 (0.01)	16.22 (0.01)	2.0-9.9	67	6.499	0.74	5.50	5.46	0.002
20.0	9.59 (0.01)	13.98 (0.01)	16.30 (0.01)	2.4-10.0	50	7.467	0.28	6.61	7.68	0.003
30.0	9.60 (0.01)	14.13 (0.01)	16.71 (0.01)	2.7-10.1	61	9.649	0.57	4.59	23.44	0.004
40.0	9.50 (0.01)	14.13 (0.02)	16.81 (0.03)	2.9-10.3	47	4.383	1.38	6.60	7.62	0.008
50.0	9.44 (0.01)	14.25 (0.03)	17.18 (0.04)	3.1-10.3	60	3.595	1.42	5.87	12.53	0.15
60.0	9.24 (0.04)	14.36 (0.08)	17.87 (0.09)	3.6-10.3	61	9.081	2.00	9.37	39.05	0.034

No. of titration curves in each percentage = 4

$U_{\text{con}} = U(NP-m) \times 10^3$ where, m = number of species.

ornithine in water-DMF mixtures (Fig. 1) reveal that the acidobasic equilibria are active in the pH range, 2.0-10.0:

Fig. 1. Alkalimetric titration curves of L-ornithine in (A) 20% DMF, (B) 40% DMF, (C) 60% DMF and (D) formation curves of L-ornithine in 40% DMF. Ligand concentrations: (a, $\square$) 0.4, (b, Δ) 0.6, (c, $\circ$) 0.8 mmol

In the modelling strategy the dimeric forms of the ligand L_2H_x are not considered as there is no drift observed in the formation curves shown in Fig. 1D for different initial ligand concentrations. The computer program SCPHD was used to prune the data obtained in different experiments

and the overall formation constants given by the program are used as initial values for final refinement. The computer program MINQUAD 75³ was used to refine the protonation constants of the amino acids. The results of the best fit models that contain the type of species and overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Tables 1 and 2.

A very low standard deviation in $\log \beta$ values indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{con} (the sum of the squares of deviations in concentrations of ligand and hydrogen ion at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, indicate that the experimental data can be represented by the model. Small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of kurtosis and skewness should be three and zero, respectively. The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals of many systems form a leptokurtic and a few form platykurtic pattern. The values of skewness recorded in the Tables are between 0.28 and 2.40. These data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution, hence, least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic R value recorded. These statistical parameters, thus show that the best fit models portray the acidobasic equilibria of L-ornithine and L-glutamic acid in water-DMF mixtures.

The comparison of analytical data for separate and pooled experiments is shown in Table 3. These data reveal that the standard deviation in the stability constant for pooled data is different from that for individual titrations which is probably the result of inter-titration variability.

Table 3. Chemical modeling for separate and pooled data of L-glutamic acid in 20% (v/v) water-DMF mixture

	log β_1 (SD)	log β_2 (SD)	log β_3 (SD)	pH range	NP	U_{curr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ^2	R
1	9.53 (0.01)	13.91 (0.01)	16.24 (0.02)	2.4-10.0	10	1.280	0.73	8.10	8.00	0.001
2	9.60 (0.01)	13.99 (0.01)	16.32 (0.02)	"	13	3.755	0.83	4.81	5.38	0.002
3	9.59 (0.01)	13.98 (0.01)	16.28 (0.01)	"	17	3.206	0.36	3.58	1.76	0.001
4	9.59 (0.01)	14.01 (0.01)	16.37 (0.02)	"	10	3.338	0.27	6.63	7.20	0.003
Average	9.58 (0.03)	13.98 (0.04)	16.30 (0.05)							
Pooled data	9.59 (0.01)	13.98 (0.01)	16.30 (0.02)	"	50	7.467	0.28	6.61	7.68	0.003

Effect of systematic errors : MINQUAD 75 does not have an in-built provision to study the effect of systematic errors in the concentrations of ingredients and electrode calibration on the magnitude of equilibrium constants. In order to rely upon the best fit chemical model for critical evaluation and application, a brief investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in influential factors like the concentrations of mineral acid, ligand and alkali. This type of investigation is useful because the data acquisition is done

under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies. Results of typical systems (Table 4) emphasise that protonation constants of carboxyl group are more affected. This may probably be due to their lower magnitude than those for amino protons. Similarly, errors in concentration of alkali and acid affect more than other factors. With the introduction of errors, the SD's are found to increase inferring the appropriateness of experimental conditions and correctness of analytical concentrations.

Fig. 2. Variation of $\log K^M$ with mole fraction (Δ) and reciprocal of dielectric constant (O) in water-DMF mixtures : (A,B,C) L-ornithine and (D,E,F) L-glutamic acid.

Effect of dielectric constant : The variation of protonation constant or change in free energy with co-solvent content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic. Born's classical treatment holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. According to this treatment, the energy of electrostatic interaction is related to dielectric constant. Hence, the logarithm of protonation constant should vary linearly as a function of the reciprocal of the dielectric constant of the medium. These plots in aqua-DMF mixtures (Fig. 2) show that, though there is linearity, some systems deviate from this trend. In the case of some mono- and dicarboxylic acids and simple phenolic ligands, electrostatic (long range, non-specific or universal) solute-solvent interactions predominate in binary mixtures of water with methanol, ethanol, dioxane or acetone as co-solvents. Only in such cases the data fit into Born model. Many workers⁴ were of the opinion that both electrostatic and non-electrostatic effects should be considered even in the case of simple acidobasic equilibria; one dominates the other depending upon the nature of solute and solvent. These amino acids can exist in anionic, zwitterionic and cationic forms in different equilibria presently investigated. The cation stabilizing nature of co-solvents, specific solvent-water interactions, charge dispersion and specific interactions of co-solvent with solute (indicated by the changes in the solubility of different species in aqua-organic mixtures) account for the deviation of classical linear relationship of $\log K^M$ with $1/D$

Effect of mole fraction : An increase in DMF concentration enhances the ion-dipole forces between proton and oxygen atom of carboxyl group of amino acids, compared to the interaction of proton and solvent donor atom. This trend is clearly seen from the data in Fig. 2 A, D and E. But in the case of simple amino groups, the converse appears to be true. However, in the case of amino groups of amino acids such a simple trend is not observed. The figures clearly depict a continuous decrease in the $\log K^M$ values upto a certain solvent parameter and further increase in co-solvent concentration resulted in the reversal of this trend. The assumption that interaction between proton and nitrogen is more compared to that between proton and oxygen of water above a certain co-solvent concentration, explains the minimum observed in the plots, for many nitrogen bases.

Complete equilibrium constant In general, the solvent molecules are neglected in modeling complex equilibria. This sometimes shows a non-linear trend due to insufficiency of the model. Later a model was proposed⁵ that includes both water and co-solvent in the solvation, as per the equation, $L(w_1H_2O, s_1S) + H^+(w_2H_2O, s_2S) \rightleftharpoons LH^+(w_3H_2O, s_3S) + wH_2O + sS$ and $K^M = K^{M*} [H_2O]_M$, where K^{M*} is the complete equilibrium constant, K^M the observed equilibrium constant and $[H_2O]_M$ the concentration of water at each of the co-solvent contents. The number of water molecules released in the acidobasic equilibria are calculated by the linear least-squares analysis of

$$j^* \log [S] + \log K^M = -\Delta G^\ddagger / (2.303RT) + \log K^W - w^* \log ([H_2O]_M/[S]_M) + j^* \log [H_2O]_M$$

where s and w are number of solvent and water molecules released and j is the sum of w and s . Typical results obtained by using the computer program ESOCR⁶ (effect of solvent on complex equilibria) by varying j between -5 and $+5$, are given in Table 5. The selection of the best of several linear equations obtained was made, based on minimum standard deviation (SD) in $\log \beta$ and maximum corrected correlation coefficient (CCC) Exner (ϕ)⁷ and Ehreusen (FEHR) parameters. This approach is preferable to conventional statistics in the case of chemical data with a few (<10) observations. The number of water molecules released during protonation is found to be 3 for many systems in the present case.

For some systems the stability constants have non-linear relation with the solvent composition. Inclusion of water and solvent molecules in the equilibrium, brought linear relationship (Fig. 4). Thus, this study emphasises that a model for complex equilibria is not complete unless water and solvent molecules are included in the coordination spheres of the species.

Table 4. Effect of errors in influential factors on the protonation constants of L-glutamic acid in 20% (v/v) water-DMF mixtures

Ingredient	% error	$\log \beta$ (SD)		
		011	012	013
$\log F^{\ddagger}$	0	9.59(1)	13.98(1)	16.29(1)
	-5	9.60(1)	14.03(1)	16.34(1)
	-2	9.59(1)	13.99(1)	16.32(1)
	+2	9.59(1)	13.97(1)	16.27(1)
	+5	9.58(1)	13.95(1)	16.24(1)
Alkali	-5	9.88(1)	14.47(2)	16.87(3)
	-2	9.71(1)	14.17(1)	16.52(2)
	+2	9.48(1)	13.78(1)	16.06(2)
	+5	9.29(2)	13.36(3)	15.70(4)
Acid	-5	9.44(1)	13.68(2)	15.85(3)
	-2	9.53(1)	13.86(1)	16.12(2)
	+2	9.65(1)	14.09(1)	16.47(2)
	+5	9.74(1)	14.27(2)	16.73(3)
Ligand	-5	9.44(1)	13.77(11)	16.12(2)
	-2	9.53(1)	13.89(8)	16.23(1)
	+2	9.65(1)	14.06(6)	16.36(1)
	+5	9.73(1)	14.17(7)	16.45(1)

[†] Correction factor, $\log f = pH_{cal} - pH_{exp}$

Fig. 3. The relation between $j \log [S] + \log K^M$ and $\log [(H_2O)/[S)]$ of (A) l-ornithine in water-DMF, (B) l-glutamic acid in water-DMF (O) $\log K_1$, (Δ) $\log K_2$, ($\square$) $\log K_3$.

Distribution diagram : The distribution plots produced using the protonation constants from the best fit models show that the formation of LH and L^- in the case of L-ornithine and LH_2 and LH^- in the case of L-glutamic acid. In

Table 5. Linear trend analysis of $\log [H_2O]/[S]$ vs $j \log [S] + \log K^M$ for acidobasic equilibria of l-glutamic acid in aqua-DMF media^a

j	Slope	SD	CCC	SI	FEHR
-5	3.8220	0.0977	0.9966	0.0039	0.0530
-4	3.1100	0.0670	0.9976	0.0028	0.0447
-3	2.3979	0.0389	0.9986	0.0016	0.0337
-2	1.6859	0.0248	0.9903	0.0113	0.0305
-1	0.9739	0.0423	0.9903	0.0113	0.0899
0	0.1789	0.0701	-0.2156	1.1940	0.8910
1	-0.4502	0.1019	0.7828	0.2534	0.4254
2	1.1623	0.1334	0.9355	0.0753	0.2319
3	1.8743	0.1652	0.9611	0.0454	0.1801
4	2.5863	0.1971	0.9707	0.0342	0.1563
5	-3.2984	0.2292	0.9755	0.0285	0.1428

0.00 < SI < 0.02 and FEHR < 0.10 indicate best fit of the model

CCC = Corrected correlation coefficient

$$= 1 - (NP-1) (RSS/TSS) / (NP-2)$$

SI = Exner parameter = $(RSS / [NP-2] \cdot TSS)^{1/2}$

FEHR = Ehreusen parameter = $(RSS/TSS)^{1/2}$

RSS = Residual sum of squares = $\sum_{i=1}^{NP} (Y_{obs(i)} - Y_{cal(i)})^2$

TSS = Total sum of squares = $\sum_{i=1}^{NP} (Y_{obs(i)} - Y_{mean})^2$

both the cases, the zwitterionic form (LH_2 in the case of L-ornithine and LH^- for l-glutamic acid) is present to an extent of 90% in the pH range 4.0–7.0. But as the co-solvent content is increased the existence of these species is restricted to a narrow pH range, due to destabilization of the zwitterions with decreased dielectric constant of the medium.

Experimental

Solutions of l-ornithine and l-glutamic acid (G.R., E. Merck) were prepared in triple-distilled water. *N,N'*-Dimethyl formamide (E. Merck, 99.5% purity) was used. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA). The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method⁸.

The titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations of DMF, maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ with KCl at 303 ± 0.05 K. Requisite amounts of water and co-solvent (DMF) were added such that the overall percentages of co-solvent were in the range 10–60% (v/v). The amount of mineral acid maintained was 1 mmol, while the concentration of the amino acid (L-ornithine or L-glutamic acid) was of the order 0.4–0.8 mmol in different experiments. An Elico LI-120 pH meter was used. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred water-DMF mixture containing inert electrolyte. Titration of strong acid with alkali was carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved. The calomel electrode was filled with water-DMF mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. Titrations with different ligand concentrations were carried out with 0.4 mol dm⁻³ KOH and the data are given in Table 6. Other experimental details are given elsewhere⁹.

Table 6 Total initial concentrations of ingredients (in mmol) in proton ligand titrations^a

[KOH] = 0.4 mol dm⁻³ V₀ = 5.0 cm³ T_{emp} = 303 K mineral acid = 1.00 mmol μ = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

DMF % (v/v)	Titration curves ^a	TLO	
		l Orn	l Glu
0.00	4	0.403	0.400
		0.604	0.601
		0.805	0.801
10.0	4	0.401	0.402
		0.602	0.602
		0.803	0.803
20.0	4	0.400	0.400
		0.601	0.600
		0.801	0.800
30.0	4	0.400	0.402
		0.600	0.602
		0.800	0.803
40.0	4	0.400	0.401
		0.601	0.601
		0.801	0.801
50.0	4	0.400	0.400
		0.601	0.600
		0.801	0.800
60.0	4	0.400	0.401
		0.600	0.601
		0.800	0.802

^aOne of the titration curves is duplicated

*V₀ = Total volume μ = ionic strength TLO = total ligand concentration

Modelling strategy The approximate protonation constants of L-ornithine and L-glutamic acid were calculated

with the computer program SCPHD. The best fit chemical model for each system investigated was arrived at using non-linear least-squares computer program MINQUAD 75, which exploits the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. The variation of stepwise protonation constants was analysed on electrostatic grounds using the program ESOCE and on the basis of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions. Some of the heuristics that are to be followed in the refinement of the stability constants were listed in our earlier publication².

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